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D1 Report from the Mentorship Programme 2021-2022

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Executive Summary

The Mentorship Programme offers one-to-one support where CESSDA partners and new member SPs requesting support are matched with experts active in the program. The purpose is to help the mentees define and realise their short-term goals. These can be strategic, policy-related, practical, or technical. The Mentorship Programme is a way to ensure that the mentee sets and works towards realistic goals with active support and encouragement from the mentor. During 2021–2022, six mentorships were carried out and this report describes the activities within the various mentorships.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

ADP	Slovenian Social Science Data Archives
APIS	Portuguese Archive of Social Information
AUSSDA	Austrian Social Science Data Archive
CDC	CESSDA Data Catalogue
CeMI	Centre for Monitoring and Research
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CMM	CESSDA Metadata Model
CNR	Italian National Research Council
CPC	Centre for Political Courage
CREDI	Centre for Development Evaluation and Social Science Research
CROSSDA	Croatian Social Science Data Archive
CSDA	Czech Social Science Data Archive
CTS	CoreTrustSeal
DAG	Data Archiving Guide
da ra	Registration agency for social science and economic data
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DAS	Data Archiving Service
DASS-BiH	Data Archive for Social Sciences in Bosnia and Herzegovina
DASSI	Data Archive for Social Science in Italy
DATICE	Icelandic Social Science Data Service
DCS	Data Centre Serbia for Social Sciences
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DMEG	Data Management Expert Guide
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
ELSST	European Language Social Science Thesaurus
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud

ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESTA	Estonian Social Science Data Archive
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
FAIRsFAIR	Fostering FAIR Data Practices in Europe
FORS	Swiss Centre of Expertise in the Social Sciences
FSD	Finnish Social Science Data Archive
GUI	Graphical User Interface
ISSDA	Irish Social Science Data Archive
ISSK-BAS	Institute for the Study of Societies and Knowledge - Bulgarian Academy of Sciences
ISSP	International Social Survey Programme
IT	Information Technology
JESDA	Joint Economic and Social Data Archive
KIIS	Kyiv International Institute of Sociology
LIDA	Lithuanian Data Archive for Social Sciences and Humanities
LISER	Luxembourg Institute of Socio-Economic Research
LSA	Latvian Sociological Association
MCA	Ministry of Civil Affairs
MK DASS	Social Science Data Archive of North Macedonia
MO	Main Office
Nesstar	Networked Social Science Tools and Resources
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OAIS	Open Archival Information System
OSF	Open Society Foundations
PADS	Polish Social Data Archive
PID	Persistent Identifier
RD	Resource Directory
RItrainPlus	Research Infrastructure Training Plus
RODA	Romanian Social Data Archive
RSU	Rīga Stradiņš University
RTU	Riga Technical University
SAS	Slovak Academy of Science
SASD	Slovak Archive of Social Data
SaW	Strengthening and Widening
SND	Swedish National Data Service
SODHA	Social Sciences and Digital Humanities Archive
SP	Service Provider
SSH	Social Science and Humanities
SSHOC	Social Science and Humanities Open Science Cloud

TRUST	Transparency Responsibility User focus Sustainability Technology
UNIMIB	University of Milan-Bicocca

Introduction

Organised one-to-one support to CESSDA ERIC partner countries and new member Service Providers (SPs) was introduced in the "CESSDA Widening Activities 2019"¹ project, which was part of the CESSDA Work Plan 2019. The programme involves active support of CESSDA partners and new member SPs by matching them with experts from CESSDA SPs who participate in the program. The Mentorship Programme has continued within the project "Widening Activities and Journals Outreach 2020"², and in subtask 1 "Mentorship Programme" in the Agenda 21–22 Widening & Outreach task 1 "Widening the CESSDA European Coverage".

This report describes the results from the Mentorship Programme 2021–2022. It provides a brief overview of the mentees' situation at the beginning of the mentorship and describes the mentees' goals for the coming years, as well as the support requested from the mentors. Mentoring activities carried out during the period are addressed, as well as the mentees' situation at the end of the mentorship and their plans for 2023. Finally, both mentees and mentors provide some reflections on the mentorship.

The Mentorship Programme 2021–2022

Objective

The objective of the Mentorship Programme 2021–2022 was the same as previous years, that is, that mentors help mentees to define and realise their strategic, policy-related, practical, or technical short-term goals. The mentors were responsible for actively accompanying their mentee partners throughout the mentorship period.

Timeline

Originally, the one-to-one support was planned to include three mentorships in 2021 and three in 2022. However, due to the continued uncertain situation with COVID-19, the start of the programme was postponed.

¹ Christina Bornatici, Iris Alfredsson, Aleksandra Bradic-Martinovic, Marijana Glavica, Peter Hegedus, Amela Kurta, Yana Leontiyeva, Vaidas Morkevičius, Irena Vipavc Brvar, Gregor Zibert. (2020). CESSDA Widening Activities 2019: Deliverable 3 - Report on the Online Support Service and the Mentorship Programme. CESSDA: Bergen.

² Christina Bornatici, Irena Vipavc Brvar, & Iris Alfredsson. (2021). Report from the Mentorship Programme and the Pilot Newsletter (1.3). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5724066>

The invitation to apply for the Mentorship Programme was sent out to twelve partners and nine member SPs on 9 July 2021. When the application period expired at the end of August, seven applications had been received.

Table 1: Invitation to and participation in the Mentorship Programme 2021–2022

Invited country	Partner or member	Invited organisation	Participation in earlier Mentorship Programme	Mentor 2021-2022
Belgium	M	SODHA	-	-
Bosnia & Herzegovina	P	CREDI	2019	ADP
Bulgaria	P	ISSK-BAS	2020	-
Croatia	M	CROSSDA	2019, 2020	-
Estonia	P	ESTA	-	-
Iceland	M	DATICE	-	SND
Ireland	M	ISSDA	2020	-
Italy	M	DASSI	2019	FORS
Kosovo	P	CPC	2019, 2020	-
Latvia	P	LSA	-	TARKI
Lithuania	P	LiDA	2019	AUSSDA
Luxembourg	P	LISER	-	-
Montenegro	P	CeMI	-	-
North Macedonia	M	MK DASS	2019	-
Poland	P	PADS	-	-
Portugal	M	APIS	2020	-
Romania	P	RODA	2020	*
Russia	P (2022)	JESDA	-	-
Serbia	M	DCS	2019	-
Slovakia	M	SASD	-	CSDA
Ukraine	P	Data Bank	-	*CSDA

*Romania withdrew from the Mentorship Programme 2021–2022 due to a lack of staff. In 2022, CSDA volunteered to mentor Ukraine SP as an in-kind support.

It was decided to merge the Mentorship Programme 2021 with the Mentorship Programme 2022 into one programme with six mentorships starting in autumn 2021 and continuing in 2022. As it was essential to be able to include on-site visits in the mentorship, this solution would increase the possibility to conduct the visits if the travel restrictions were to end in 2021.

The initial contacts between mentor and mentee were made in October 2021. The mentorships were then carried out through regular Zoom meetings and, in most cases, an on-site visit.

At the end of 2022 most of the mentorships were finalised, but there was a request for an extension of the project to enable an on-site visit to one of the mentorships. After consultation with all task members and CESSDA MO, it was decided to prolong the task until the end of February 2023.

Selection of mentees and mentors

In early September 2021, the members of the Mentoring Program task held a Zoom meeting where they discussed the applications and how to match mentors and mentees. The team of mentors consisted of staff from ADP, AUSSDA, CSDA, FORS, SND, and TARKI.

When mentees and mentors were paired, countries were chosen by geographic proximity. The reason for this was to facilitate on-site visits, as the COVID-19 situation still made travelling uncertain.

As there were seven applications for six mentors, this resulted in a proposal that Latvia could participate in a planned Dataverse event, but refrain from the direct one-to-one mentorship as it still lacks an institutionalised data archiving service (DAS) for the social sciences. Later in the autumn of 2021, the Romanian SP RODA withdrew its application due to staff shortages, and TARKI became the mentor for Latvia.

Other activities within the Mentorship Programme

At the beginning of the Mentorship Programme, the team met once a month to support each other in the start-up of the mentorships and to discuss the possibility of common activities.

When reviewing the request for support, it was found that most applicants requested support related to Dataverse. Since several of the mentors lacked expertise in matters related to Dataverse, the team discussed a possibility of redistributing resources and organising a Dataverse event, tailored for the mentees, was discussed. Unfortunately, it was not possible to implement this within the 2021-2022 Mentorship Programme.

In collaboration with the Resource Directory (RD) team, an introduction to the RD was held in May 2022. Twelve participants from the Mentorship Programme gathered for a presentation of the RD and a demonstration based on different use cases, followed by feed-back from the participants and a discussion on development strategies and future activities.

The concept of the three Mentorship Programmes has been similar over the years. The only major change has been the addition of on-site visits in 2020. After three rounds of the CESSDA Mentorship Programme and with experiences from twenty mentorships, it was time for a team from FORS, GESIS and SND to develop a new and updated concept for the programme presented in another deliverable from this subtask.³

³ Alfredsson, Iris, Bishop, Libby, & Bornatici, Christina. (2023). D2 Strategy for the Development of the Mentorship Programme. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5554455>

Mentorship guidelines

Guidelines for the Mentorship Programme were developed and agreed upon during the first programme in 2019 and have since been maintained in subsequent programmes.

The mentor:

- is the mentee's contact person during the mentoring period;
- is responsible for actively supporting their mentee partner throughout the mentoring period and having regular meetings;
- documents the collaboration;
- maintains regular contact with other mentors to share their mentees' needs and together find solutions to help the mentees when necessary.

The mentee:

- agrees to collaborate with the mentor;
- provides a final report on the mentorship received:
 - reporting the goals and activities realised during the year;
 - discussing what went well and what could be improved for future mentoring activities;
 - updating the situation and plans for the coming year.

Mentorship between ADP and DASS-BiH

The situation at DASS-BiH at the beginning of the mentorship

DASS-BiH (Data Archive for Social Sciences in Bosnia and Herzegovina) is the national service to ensure long-term preservation and dissemination of social science research data in Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH). It is an organisational unit of the Centre for Development Evaluation and Social Science Research (CREDI). The data archive aims to provide a vital research data resource for researchers, teachers, students, and all other interested users. In addition to long-term preservation, the DASS-BiH performs data-level curation, including brief checking, basic metadata and/or documentation, creating new formats, and enhancing documentation; it also edits the deposited data for accuracy.

DASS-BiH can be seen as a domain or subject-based repository, institutional repository, and national repository system. It is a subject-based repository for long-term preservation of data collected from social science research in the following fields: economy, education, employment and labour, political science, psychology, sociology, society and culture, and social welfare policy. As its managing institution is in social science research, data collected within CREDI's projects are preserved in DASS-BiH, which is therefore seen as an institutional repository. Currently, it is the only social science data archive in the country. DASS-BiH is in the process of obtaining official recognition as a national data archive, issued by the Ministry of Civil Affairs (MCA), which oversees science and education affairs in the

country. The recognition is expected to be part of Bosnia and Herzegovina's official accession to CESSDA ERIC and to obtain member status.

Currently, primary users of DASS-BiH services are university researchers and teachers, university students (doctoral, master, bachelor), and researchers from other public research institutions (e.g., scientific institutes, government organisations). DASS-BiH provides basic curation for deposited datasets at its current level of development. That includes preparation of metadata files and necessary activities related to data anonymization, conversion of data formats to those suitable for long-term preservation, and activities associated with maintaining accessibility and findability of data.

The services are provided to end-users following the FAIR principles under the Open Archival Information System (OAIS), including the pre-ingest phase. To increase the demand for DASS-BiH's services and to help its community to understand the benefits of long-term preservation, DASS-BiH continuously provides education and organises different events to promote these practices. To become recognizable by the research community as a trustworthy repository, DASS-BiH was in the process of obtaining CoreTrustSeal (CTS) certification, supported by the FAIRsFAIR project.

Goals for 2021-2022

At the beginning of mentorship support, DASS-BiH planned to complete the key steps towards obtaining the CESSDA ERIC full membership status. These included several activities:

- Continue to advocate the MCA to sign and submit a formal request for CESSDA ERIC membership.
- Advocate the MCA to pass legislation that will make social science data archiving mandatory, at least for data produced within projects funded from the government budget.
- Install software to increase data findability and visibility.
- Continue working with the community of users to train them how to use new services and understand procedures in accessing and depositing data.
- Increase the number of datasets collected and published in the Data Catalogue.
- Obtain CoreTrustSeal certification.

Support requested from the Mentorship Programme

Since DASS-BiH was established three years ago, it is currently in the middle-stage development, where most of internal and external procedures are developed. The initial development of policies and procedures started within the CESSDA Mentorship Programme in 2019, where DASS-BiH mentor was TÁRKI Data Archive. The support provided was of particular importance in its early-stage development, and therefore DASS-BiH staff believe

that mentorship support is an effective way to advance services and acquire knowledge from more experienced partners in the network.

In line with the DASS-BiH goals for the following period, DASS-BiH staff were interested in receiving support through the Mentorship Programme on the use of software and on practical guidelines to improve the findability and visibility of data. The DASS-BiH Data Catalogue⁴ was based on a simple web application where users can find basic information about the deposited studies and access the category of a dataset. DASS-BiH wanted to improve the Data Catalogue application by installing Dataverse, used by more experienced social science data archives. DASS-BiH had already purchased a server and employed an IT person to install a basic Dataverse application. DASS-BiH staff asked to receive support in the form of training and guidance on how to use the software. DASS-BiH also became a member of the da|ra Consortium and initiated a procedure for obtaining DOI prefix, and a brief training on how to incorporate DOI into the Dataverse system would also be useful. In addition to training in the use of software, DASS-BiH asked to receive support in developing training materials for depositors and users on how to use Dataverse to review the Data Catalogue and self-archiving function content.

The mentorship activities during 2021–2022

After introductory discussions, a rough plan for mentorship activities was outlined: two online sessions on Dataverse in spring of 2022 (1. Introduction to Dataverse, possibilities in Dataverse, modifications to Dataverse, Q&A session; 2. Introduction to workflow procedures based on Dataverse) and an on-site visit to ADP (focused on practical training in Dataverse, continuation of work on DASS-BiH Workflow procedures, short introduction to the CESSDA Data Archiving Guide (DAG), increased visibility within CESSDA and other stakeholders). Due to time restrictions, only the first online session/webinar was conducted, while the activities planned for the second online session were conducted during the on-site visit.

The DASS-BiH visit to ADP took place in May 2022 and combined activities from both the CESSDA Mentorship Programme and the RITrainPLUS project.⁵ Several work sessions were prepared: Dataverse (data catalogue, data access, plugins, customizations, Weblate tool, registration of persistent identifiers), training in how to develop workflows for Dataverse, presentation of ADP tools, E-permanent storage application and future technical development; presentation of the ADP's current workflow procedures (deposit, curation, archiving, dissemination); presentation of the statement on delivery of materials, DMP for PhD students, researchers, research institutes; and training in how to develop DASS-BiH workflow procedures (pre-acquisition and OAIS, training materials). Several fruitful discussions developed in the sessions, as well as a first draft revision of a DASS-BiH workflow procedure, which was then finalised after the study visit took place.

⁴ "DASS-BiH Data Catalogue: <https://dass.credi.ba/data-catalogue/>" [2023-02-03]

⁵ "RITrainplus: <https://ritrainplus.eu/>" [2023-03-11]

Meetings with representatives from the Slovenian Ministry of Education, Science and Sport (discussion about Research infrastructures, the law on scientific research, EOSC, open science), the journal Javnost, the Public Opinion and Mass Communication Research Centre, and the Slovenian OpenAIRE were also organised.

The situation at DASS-BiH at the end of 2022 and plans for 2023

At the end of 2022, DASS-BiH had completed most of the activities that were planned for this year. At the beginning of the year, DASS-BiH received the CoreTrustSeal certificate and promoted it within its designated community. A Dataverse instance of DASS-BiH Data Catalogue was installed to increase data findability and visibility. The staff of DASS-BiH is adding data collection and materials to the Data Catalogue. Currently, there are no publicly available datasets and collections but DASS-BiH will make them available once the entire migration from the previous version of the Data Catalogue is finished. During 2022, DASS-BiH staff worked on promoting open science principles, in particular long-term data preservation and reuse, within its research communities and towards the BiH Ministry of Civil Affairs. DASS-BiH staff also worked on the revision of policies and procedures to align them with changes in the Data Catalogue operations, partly through the CESSDA Mentorship Programme. In terms of plans for 2023, DASS-BiH staff will work on uploading datasets to their Dataverse catalogue and invest some time into preparing and implementing a training for data users to equip them with a new technical solution for the data catalogue. DASS-BiH will continue working on the promotion of data preservation/reuse within the research community, as well as organise several events to advocate for full CESSDA ERIC membership status together with representatives of universities who support DASS-BiH work. With these events, DASS-BiH plans to acquire more datasets and promote the usage of currently available datasets.

Reflections on the mentorship from DASS BiH and ADP

A particularly important part of the cooperation in the mentorship programme is an on-site visit, where several in-depth discussions about the various aspects that data archives are working on can develop, helping both the mentor and the mentee. DASS-BiH staff benefited from the mentorship support in several different ways. During the entire mentorship support, it was valuable to gain practical insights into the advocacy strategies for including data archives in the research landscape of the country and how different components around the data archive help this process. DASS-BiH staff is equipped to understand and use different Dataverse components and how to integrate them into everyday activities. During the mentorship support, the DASS-BiH Workflow procedure was reviewed and revised to reflect new developments in the catalogue's technical infrastructure, as well as modified procedures for data deposit and access. As a result of the mentorship support, CREDI initiated additional activities for DASS-BiH, such as the development of the action plan to further advocate for full membership of Bosnia and Herzegovina in CESSDA ERIC, as well as

activities related to education and awareness raising towards more open science practices in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Mentorship between AUSSDA and LiDA

The situation at LiDA at the beginning of the mentorship

From 2019, the Lithuanian Data Archive for Social Sciences and Humanities (LiDA) has been transforming the IT infrastructure of its services. The services were created more than 10 years ago, and since then, major developments have occurred in the field of data archiving and curation: the FAIR principles were published for data management and curation, the CoreTrustSeal for certification of trustworthy data repositories was launched, and the TRUST principles were developed for digital repositories. To comply with these new standards, the existing IT infrastructure had to be updated so that LiDA can remain trustworthy and a leading national archive for social sciences and humanities in Lithuania. Therefore, the decision was made to move from a Nesstar/FEDORA based IT infrastructure to a Dataverse based IT infrastructure. The desired outcome was that the transfer to the Dataverse based IT infrastructure would best enable LiDA to follow the FAIR and TRUST principles and acquire a CoreTrustSeal certification. Currently, the Dataverse deployment is almost finalised.⁶ However, LiDA still needs to transform its processes for data ingest, documentation, storage, and curation, so that they are best adapted to the Dataverse software.

Goals for 2021-2022

These efforts are envisioned as necessary for the successful transfer of LiDA's data sets into the new IT infrastructure:

- Installation of the Handle PID service into the Dataverse repository.
- Customisation of the Dataverse GUI and translation into Lithuanian.
- Installation of the most relevant external tools (especially dedicated to file level metadata management and file previewing).
- Customisation of dataset licensing, restricted access, and metadata fields for the Dataverse repository.
- Transfer of the existing datasets into the Dataverse repository (transformation of documentation from DDI 1.2.2 into DDI 2.5, at the same time implementing compliance with the CESSDA Metadata Model (CMM)).
- Integration of "pyDataverse" tools into the data curation processes.
- Development of data ingest, documentation, storage, and publication guidelines for the LiDA Dataverse repository.

⁶ <https://dataverse.lidata.eu>

Support requested from the Mentorship Programme

Support and guidance with the highest priority was seen in these areas:

- The process of translating the Dataverse GUI into other languages (especially, in the view of the constant need for upgrading the Dataverse deployment).
- Best practice for transforming Nesstar DDI documentation (1.2.2) into Dataverse DDI documentation (2.5) for the existing datasets while staying compliant with the CMM.
- Best practices for integrating “pyDataverse” tools into the data curation process.
- Challenges and opportunities of integrating the Dataverse repository into data ingest, documentation, storage, and publication processes of data archives.

The mentee and mentor discussed the mentorship goals and agreed to have online meetings to exchange knowledge and seek out opportunities for collaboration. At the end of the programme, an on-site training at LiDA should be conducted with the added value of teaching processes relevant to be CoreTrustSeal certified.

The mentorship activities during 2021–February 2023

One online meeting has been conducted and several information requests have been processed. Information requests and discussions included information about archive processes, Dataverse integration in CDC by means of a proxy, the pyDataverse software, and the use of the CESSDA Metadata Validator.⁷

From February 6th to 8th 2023, AUSSDA staff member Veronika Heider visited the Lithuanian Archive LiDA at Kaunas University of Technology (KTU). She coordinates data ingest and processing at AUSSDA. As a senior data curator, she works closely with depositors to make metadata, data, and documentation in the AUSSDA Dataverse findable and usable. The agenda of the 3-day visit centred around data ingest, access, and preservation. After getting to know each other on day 1, day 2 delivered training on curating social science data, documentation, and metadata in a well-documented way and as replicable as possible. The CoreTrustSeal certification was presented, as AUSSDA has been certified since 2017 and LiDA indicated a high interest in the process of application. As both archives use Dataverse as their repository, day 3 was about the software and processes that both archives must work with. Representatives from the Faculty of Social Sciences, Art and Humanities, and the IT department contributed to the active exchange between LiDA and AUSSDA.

The situation at LiDA at the end of 2022 and plans for 2023

- Translation of the Dataverse repository GUI into Lithuanian is being implemented. The first draft of the translation of Dataverse 5.6 GUI was finalised in October 2022 using the CESSDA developed Weblate tool⁸ and consultation via SSHOC Dataverse

⁷ “CESSDA Metadata Validator: <https://cmv.cessda.eu/#!validation>” [2023-02-03]

⁸ “Weblate tool: <https://weblate-sshoc.cessda.eu>” [2023-02-03]

Translation events.⁹ The next two steps are planned for December 2022 and January 2023:

- installation of the GUI translation (following a Dataverse guide¹⁰),
- corrections of the first draft of the translations.
- Approximately 500 data sets were in a DDI 1.2.2 version and needed to be converted into DDI 2.5 and Dataverse fields. At first, the idea was to use/develop a tool for automatic conversion. However, after discussion with the mentors it became clear that Dataverse DDI 2.5 version is not fully compliant with the CMM. In addition, many fields from the old datasets must be updated, so automatic conversion would not be particularly beneficial. It was decided to do the metadata conversions manually. Also, a solution for making metadata compliant with the CMM was found and partially implemented. The general idea is to have two separate language data descriptions in Dataverse JSON and transform them (using a crosswalk) into bilingual DDI 2.5, compliant with the CMM. This requires adding an additional metadata export format to the standard Dataverse metadata export formats (it can then be harvested via OAI-PMH).
- After discussion with the mentors the idea of using "pyDataverse" in the standard ingest was abandoned. However, some automatization tools of metadata publishing on the Dataverse repository are needed for "mass metadata changes", that is, when changes in certain metadata fields (for example, when standards for entering keywords, subjects, data types etc. change, or licensing terms change) in all the datasets are needed. Relevant tools are pyDataverse¹¹, a tool by Julian Gautier¹² and the tool easyDataverse.¹³

Reflections on the mentorship from LiDA and AUSSDA

At the beginning of the mentee-mentoring relationship, LiDA and AUSSDA agreed to a reduced mentoring activity due to limited resources at that time.. Based on this, an online meeting was held and several requests for information have been processed. There has been no request for in-depth consultation on specific topics following the initial enquiries. The on-site training was an effective delivery of knowledge to LiDA staff. It was seen as more effective than an online training as the trainer was able to engage more with LiDA staff and university staff. To summarise the relationship: The mentor and staff at AUSSDA filled a supportive role to deliver CESSDA and AUSSDA knowledge for various activities. LiDa was able to continue to achieve its goals.

⁹ "SSHOC Dataverse Translation events:

<https://sshopencloud.eu/events/sshoc-dataverse-translation-follow-event>" [2023-02-03]

¹⁰ <https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/installation/config.html#internationalization>

¹¹ <https://github.com/gdcc/pyDataverse>, <https://pydataverse.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

¹² <https://github.com/jggautier/dataverse-scripts>

¹³ <https://github.com/gdcc/easyDataverse>

Mentorship between CSDA and SASD

The situation at SASD at the beginning of the mentorship

The situation at the Slovak Archive of Social Data (SASD) at the beginning of the mentorship in September 2021 was given by focusing on archiving the collection of the social science data concerning the COVID-19 pandemic. The Institute for Sociology at the Slovak Academy of Science (SAS) is an active partner in the repeated cross-sectional survey research “How are you, Slovakia?” and part of the cooperation was that data are archived and accessible in SASD (research continues in 2021, 2022 and 2023).

During 2020, the first year of the pandemic, 7 large-scale surveys were conducted on a representative sample of Slovakia's online population, which provided up-to-date data on the public perceptions of the actual situation and issues. There was also additional COVID-19 research administered at the Institute of Sociology, SAS, in preparation for archiving (Values and Society in COVID-19 Pandemic, November 2020), public opinion data were focused on six main issues: social trust, politics and democracy, conspiracy theories, vaccination, climate change and environment, and free time.

From the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, there was an increase in the visibility of survey data in media, public administration and everyday life – active knowledge utilisation. Findings from the survey series *How are you, Slovakia?* have been on the front pages in mass media since the beginning of the pandemic, in TV reports, in the editorials of magazines or press releases. The researchers cooperating in the project were regular guests of radio and TV shows, podcasts and so on. Together, more than 450 media references were available until June 2021, as well as more than 30 interviews in podcasts, shows and TV reports.

There was an increasing interest in survey methodology within the scientific community as well as in media – sampling, on-line panels, new topics, and new research questions (also sensitive issues), face-to-face interviewing during pandemic, and web-surveys limitations.

Regarding the CoreTrustSeal certification, SASD was in contact with the SSHOC project and received their certification support.

Goals for 2021-2022

The goals were defined as practical and technical:

- preparation of new datasets on COVID-19 research for archiving
- securing that a majority of the datasets have all requirements needed for DOI
- active development in the CoreTrustSeal certification process.

Support requested from the Mentorship Programme

As defined, the Mentorship Programme was initiated to assist CESSDA partners in defining and realising their short-term goals - strategic, policy, practical, or technical aims.

For SASD, this kind of help is interesting and it would be useful to have a more experienced partner for consultation when there are unclear issues connected to archiving and providing data – strategic, practical, or technical.

During the Mentorship Programme SASD had an interest to discuss “ad hoc” with the mentor when dealing with practical or technical problems, or issues that were unclear to SASD. SASD also welcomed instructions on new tools and their introduction to the SASD operations.

The mentorship activities during 2021–2022

A face-to-face meeting was held between CSDA and SASD on 11 November 2021, where the following was discussed:

- Setting priorities and strategy for the mentorship, specifying the needs.
- Brainstorming regarding the Dataverse workshop; detailed discussion about Dataverse, CoreTrustSeal, agreements between the archive and depositors.

The outcome of the meeting was: short-term goals were set, i.e. the date of the following online and offline meetings, initial ideas about which issues that will be important for SASD, and ideas for joint cooperation.

Activities during the mentorship:

- An online meeting was held on 17 February 2022 where the situation of SASD was discussed and goals for 2022 were set. The discussion targeted several important issues that SASD requested to have explained, i.e. obtaining the CoreTrustSeal, transition to Dataverse, consultation about DOI assignments, and ethical aspects of data archiving and sharing.
- Continuous email consultations over the course of the year.
- CSDA shared their most relevant training materials about data management and data archiving with SASD.
- CSDA forwarded suggestions and invitations to training events to SASD.
- A face-to-face consultation between SASD and CSDA was held in Prague. The consultation focused on Dataverse, CTS, and Nesstar.

The situation at SASD at the end of 2022 and plans for 2023

SASD activities related to the mentorship in 2022

- SASD and CSDA participated in a joint conference on COVID-19 data from the Czech Republic and Slovakia (on 29 November 2021 on Zoom, with presentations by M. Bahna and K. Strapcová)
- SASD disseminated information about CESSDA and CSDA events, i.e. data management and archiving training, seminars, webinars and workshops
- SASD targeted promotion of SASD and CESSDA services at lectures and scientific events
- SASD members attended several CESSDA training events and studied training materials such as DMEG.

SASD plans for 2023:

- Export additional Slovakian data to CDC
- Preparation for obtaining CoreTrustSeal (CTS); SASD plans the consultation with CSDA regarding the new CTS requirements for 2023–2025
- Continuous archiving of new data in the SASD (mainly data from the “*How are you, Slovakia?*” project and ISSP data)
- Processing requirements for da|ra (DOI)
- Continuous promotion of SASD and CESSDA services.

Reflections on the mentorship from SASD and CSDA

SASD's expectations for the mentorship program were met. SASD particularly appreciates the technical support and ad hoc consultations that helped resolve technical issues in archiving and providing data. It is important to note that CSDA has been a close partner to SASD even before the formal mentorship started. This is a result of the close cooperation between the Institute of Sociology at the Slovak Academy of Sciences and the Institute of Sociology at the Czech Academy of Sciences. The Mentorship Programme helped make this collaboration more structured and frequent in 2022. SASD would appreciate continued collaboration with CSDA, especially in the context of the CTS certification process and the new CTS Guideline requirements for 2023–2025.

CSDA established the mentorship plan in collaboration with SASD at the end of 2021. This plan has largely been met. The online and on-site meetings took place and members of the CSDA provided the information requested by the SASD. CSDA prepared documents containing important resources related to data archiving and data management. SASD was primarily interested in CoreTrustSeal and DOI assignment issues; the members of CSDA provided consultations on these issues. CSDA answered SASD's e-mails requesting consultation.

Mentorship between FORS and DASSI

The situation at DASSI at the beginning of the mentorship

DASSI (Data Archive for Social Science in Italy) is a research infrastructure established in 2021 through a collaboration between the University of Milan-Bicocca (seat of the UniData - Bicocca Data Archive) and the National Research Council (CNR), with institutional and financial support from the Ministry of University and Research. The objectives of DASSI are the following:

- acquisition, preservation, and distribution of data produced by the scientific community in the social sciences and humanities domain
- design, implementation, and supply of services for data management and distribution services
- training on FAIR data, interoperability, and Open Science.

After years of collaboration between CESSDA and UniData, on July 1 2021, Italy formally became a member of CESSDA ERIC, and DASSI has been recognised as the National Service Provider of the infrastructure.

To implement the activities of DASSI, two working groups have been set up with the following objectives:

- WG Infrastructure: the objective is to identify and implement the technical infrastructure of DASSI for storage and distribution of research data
- WG Policy and Documentation: the objective is to draft the documentation and describe the procedures for proper functioning of DASSI in terms of acquisition, preservation, distribution, and provision of services to the community.

Until the activities of the WGs are concluded, the activities of data acquisition, preservation, and distribution are carried out by the UniData - Bicocca Data Archive Center.

Goals for 2021-2022

According to the timeline established in common agreement between CNR and UNIMIB, the essential activities of DASSI are intended to be made operational within the first half of 2022. It is intended to carry out the following activities:

- implementation of the technical infrastructure that will ensure the operation of the essential activities of DASSI, in particular:
 - preservation of data according to the OAIS standard
 - data distribution to the community.

CNR, which is responsible for this activity, will make available the infrastructure that already exists and is used by the Italian nodes of other ERIC infrastructures (for instance, DARIAH). For data distribution, the WG Infrastructure is evaluating the use of the Dataverse platform.

- definition of the procedures for data acquisition, storage and distribution and drafting of the necessary documentation for the operation of the Service Provider. This activity, coordinated by UNIMIB, will be based on the procedures and workflow already implemented by the UniData - Bicocca Data Archive, as they are compliant with the OAIS model and the CESSDA ERIC recommendations.

In particular, the WG Policy and Documentation will be responsible for drafting the documents necessary to ensure the proper functioning of the pre-ingest (Deposit form, Collection Policy, Appraisal criteria, Preservation Policy), ingest (Data curation procedures, Metadata Model), and data access (Data Dissemination Policy, End User Licence) phases.

Support requested from the Mentorship Programme

The support requested from CESSDA concerns the monitoring and control of the work carried out by the WGs in relation to the objectives established. In particular:

- WG Infrastructure: advice, suggestions, and indications regarding the "technical" aspects to be taken into consideration, both in the implementation of data storage procedures (in accordance with the OAIS model), and in the selection of the data distribution platform;
- WG Policy and Documentation: advice, suggestions, and indications on the policies to be adopted and on the documents that will be produced (also evaluating them in view of a possible future request for CoreTrustSeal certification).

The support provided will allow DASSI to carry out its activities in compliance with the standards required by CESSDA and, at the same time, to benefit from the experience of other European data repositories.

The mentorship activities during 2021–2022

After defining the mentorship plan, the activities focused on reviewing the documentation necessary for the functioning of DASSI. From an operational point of view, a document review procedure was defined, consisting of the submission of the draft by DASSI, review by FORS and online discussion in regular meetings. It was thus possible to review and complete the draft of the following documents: DASSI statutes, Data Acquisition Policy, Deposit Agreement, and Metadata Model. In this way, it was possible to improve the clarity and the effectiveness of the documentation, thanks to the long experience of the mentor.

From the point of view of archiving procedures and IT infrastructure, the site visit at FORS in September 2022 was very productive. During the visit, it was possible to discuss both the

archiving business – and related issues – and their implementation from a technical point of view (storage, metadata editing, data distribution). The visit to FORS was also very fruitful in terms of understanding the organisational structure and how a data archive works in its day-to-day operations. Finally, it was possible to discuss in depth the outreach activities to raise awareness and engage more effectively with the researchers' community.

The situation at DASSI at the end of 2022 and plans for 2023

Thanks to the Mentorship Programme, it was possible to complete the drafting of the necessary documentation and policies for DASSI. On the technical side, several delays slowed down the implementation of the IT infrastructure. By the end of 2022, the DASSI team will test its system for study archiving and publishing, and finalise the documentation of its archiving workflow. At the same time, DASSI has commissioned an external company to create its website and define a brand strategy.

The archive will be fully operational in early 2023. Subsequently, activities will focus on making DASSI and its services as visible as possible. The main goal is to acquire new studies and expand the user base of the data and services offered by DASSI.

Reflections on the mentorship from DASSI and FORS

On DASSI's side, the mentorship experience with FORS was beneficial for sharing and improving the policies and documentation of the new service provider. The expertise of the FORS team helped DASSI to address the main issues concerning data storage, archiving, documentation, and distribution. The visit to FORS, in addition, not only helped provide more insight into the operation of a data archive but also strengthened the bond between the two teams and the sense of belonging to the CESSDA community.

FORS maintained regular contact with DASSI through online meetings during the mentorship period. A main contact person at FORS was always present during these meetings, other employees at the data archive joined and provided consultations depending on the topics discussed. During DASSI's visit, this was broadened to also include staff from FORS teams outside the data archive (e.g., IT, communications, and management). The various discussions proved that one can always learn from one another, regardless of the maturity level. Finally, thanks to DASSI's visit, FORS colleagues that are less involved in CESSDA activities could experience international collaborations for data archives and get a better understanding of CESSDA, and FORS's involvement in it.

Mentorship between SND and DATICE

The situation at DATICE at the beginning of the mentorship

At the start of the mentorship 2021, the Icelandic Social Science Data Service (DATICE) was working to obtain a CoreTrustSeal (CTS) certification and had recently secured a 2-year

funding to work on issues related to the certification and the improvement of DATICE's technical infrastructure. However, DATICE still had to secure funding for daily operations, and this was considered a major priority. To expand DATICE's services and form a national network of data services was considered an important effort to achieve this. Negotiations with three other universities in Iceland were planned to continue during the autumn of 2021 with the aim to draft a cooperation agreement. It was expected that most support functions would be handled by DATICE's head office at University of Iceland. Another vital issue in 2021 was to develop ways to measure the impact of DATICE's services, and to communicate these outcomes to the relevant stakeholders with the main goal of obtaining stable funding.

Goals for 2021-2022

- Develop coordination operations between different members of the service network
- Further develop and document DATICE's workflows
- Develop staff training procedures
- Develop ways to measure the impact of DATICE services and communication to stakeholders
- Enhance the technical infrastructure (e.g., issues related to Dataverse and the CESSDA Data Catalogue).

Support requested from the Mentorship Programme

DATICE was interested in receiving input on how to coordinate its operations nationally and wanted to focus on practical documentation and staff training, with an emphasis on developing and documenting a reliable workflow for all involved (e.g., data management handbook). This fitted well with DATICE's goal of achieving a CTS certification, which emphasised the importance of accurate documentation. In addition, DATICE wanted input on impact measurement and communication strategies, with a focus on obtaining stable funding. Finally, guidance on data-harvesting, especially on how to make DATICE's metadata harvestable by the CESSDA Data Catalogue, was requested.

The mentorship activities during 2021–2022

A DATICE visit to SND was planned even before the Icelandic application to the Mentorship Programme. The visit was funded by an ERASMUS staff exchange grant and took place 29 November–3 December 2021. The objective of the visit was to learn from SND and to establish future collaboration and networks. The visit focused on the following parts:

- The structure of SND and how its network of higher education institutions and research institutes works.
- How SND coordinates and conducts the teaching and training activities offered to researchers.
- How SND runs its data management at the national level.

- How SND runs its promotional activities and handles communications with key stakeholders.
- How SND evaluates the impact of its services.

The visit could also be seen as the start of the mentorship. During the 5-day visit each day was dedicated to two major information blocks, covering the following topics: Background; International cooperation; Consortium & network; Support to the universities; Data organisation system, metadata profiles and data management handbook; IT; Sensitive data; Training; CoreTrustSeal certification; and Communication. About ten of the SNDs staff were involved in the sessions. The visit also included a presentation of DATICE to all SND staff, as well as planning of the CESSDA mentorship.

During the planning of the mentorship, it was decided to aim for recurring Zoom meetings every four weeks. The first meeting was held on 10 January 2022. The main topic was the DATICE Handbook, but also the consequences of DATICE's only permanent employee leaving DATICE later in the spring. In the following months it was possible to continue to meet via Zoom approximately every month to discuss the content of the DATICE Handbook, but also other things related to data services. Due to staff shortages, there were no meetings in the latter part of 2022. The meetings and review of the handbook have resumed during the extension of the task in early 2023.

The situation at DATICE at the end of 2022 and plans for 2023

DATICE made considerable progress towards becoming a fully-fledged data service in 2022, although it still lacks stable funding for operations. Based on funding from the Icelandic Infrastructure Fund, cooperation was established with three other universities, Reykjavik University, Bifrost University and the University of Akureyri, who are now all involved in the work of DATICE. A new website was set up under a new domain name.¹⁴ Icelandic was included in the third version of the ELSST in September 2022 and work continues on reviewing, improving and updating the Icelandic translation. Towards the end of October 2022 a CoreTrustSeal Application was submitted, but advice on the application and application procedure was provided by FSD through the EOSC-Nordic project that DATICE participated in with a special emphasis on the uptake of the FAIR guiding principles. In December 2022, DATICE applied for a grant from the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation to continue building the tools and services of DATICE in cooperation with the three universities mentioned before. A grant of 200,000 EUR was awarded for that purpose in February 2023.

Future plans of DATICE are to explore possibilities with the administration of the University of Iceland to extend the service and use of the Dataverse server to other disciplines than social sciences in order to facilitate stable funding for the data service.

¹⁴ "DATICE website: <https://datice.is/is>" [2023-03-26]

Reflections on the mentorship from DATICE and SND

The mentorship from SND has been a tremendous help, especially with respect to guidance on developing and documenting workflows. A draft version of the internal data management handbook was discussed in our last online meeting. SND suggested some changes to the structure of the handbook, so that it would not only serve as an internal handbook but would also address the research community and wider society as a whole, and thus also serve as marketing material. This is now being worked on.

DATICE appreciates not only the technical support provided by SND, but even more the moral support and encouragement provided throughout the mentorship period.

Mentorship between TARKI and LSSDA

The situation at LSSDA at the beginning of the mentorship

The Latvian Social Sciences Data Archive (LSSDA) was established in 1996 and operated as a basic level data archiving service (DAS) until about 2009. Since 2016, the Latvian Sociological Association (LSA) has been involved in a collaboration with CESSDA to plan the establishment of a potential DAS. In 2017, the first plan to establish a national social science data service in Latvia was developed by a LSA task force within the CESSDA SaW project.¹⁵ No major progress towards realising this plan has been made since then.

The 'Latvian Open Science Strategy 2021-2027'¹⁶ was prepared by the Ministry of Education and Science and is structured around three pillars: "Open Access to Scientific Publications", "FAIR Research Data" and "Citizen Science". The Open Science Strategy includes undertaking several significant initiatives, such as:

- Creating a Joint ICT Services Center for Higher Education and Research, to improve the governance and quality of joint ICT services
- Developing a "DataverseLV" research data repository network, with a central node where all researchers can freely publish their research data
- Implementing a Data Steward program (approx. 20 data stewards based in research institutions in Latvia)
- Requiring Data Management Plans (DMPs) for all projects funded by state-funded research programs
- Creating an Open Science monitoring system
- Encouraging greater participation of Latvian research institutions in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)

¹⁵ "CESSDA SaW: <https://cessdasaw.eu/>" [2023-02-22]

¹⁶ "Latvian Open Science Strategy 2021-2027: <https://www.izm.gov.lv/en/article/latvian-open-science-strategy-2021-2027-now-english>" [2023-02-22]

It is likely that the strategy will put stronger institutional pressure on scientific institutions to start building their own data repositories, or to use existing ones.

In 2020, the Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Latvia made a conceptual decision to create a network of national research data repositories using the Dataverse software. The administration of the central Dataverse was to be entrusted to the National Library of Latvia, later this was changed to the Cross-Sectoral Coordination Center or another institution of the Republic of Latvia.

Three research data archives have recently been established in Latvia:

- CLARIN-LV¹⁷ is a CTS certified repository of language resources and tools created in Latvia. Since 2020 it is registered as a CLARIN C-center.
- The publication and research data repository ORTUS¹⁸ at the second largest university in Latvia, Riga Technical University (RTU). The purpose of the archive is to collect and store scientific research data and other relevant information in all areas of knowledge of RTU. Recently they have started experimenting with a Dataverse installation.
- Since 2020 there is an active data repository at Rīga Stradiņš University (RSU),¹⁹ the third largest university in Latvia. So far only 29 datasets have been uploaded.

In the absence of a national framework for how research data produced with public funds should be handled, institutional behaviour is largely unregulated and researchers choose ad hoc solutions. This usually means that data is stored on personal computers or in the cloud and, in the best case, shared within a certain research group. Personal contacts are typically used to obtain data for reuse, or data is sought and requested from the specific institution that commissioned and paid for the study.

Goals for 2021-2022

The goal for 2021-2022 was to take a first step towards establishing a Latvian Social Science Data Archive by installing Dataverse and creating a prototype of a DAS.

- Install Dataverse for the Latvian Sociological Association's "The Latvian Social Sciences Data Archive" and upload some data sets in test mode.
- Create a realistic prototype for a DAS.
- Set rules for data storage in the DAS.

Support requested from the Mentorship Programme

The support requested from the Mentorship Programme mainly concerned Dataverse issues.

- Dataverse installation and configuration according to CESSDA standards.
- Training in data set upload and metadata description of data sets.

¹⁷ "CLARIN-Latvia: <https://repository.clarin.lv/repository/xmlui/#>" [2023-02-22]

¹⁸ "RTU repository: <https://ortus.rtu.lv/science/en/datamodule/>" [2023-03-10]

¹⁹ "RSU data repository: <https://dataverse.rsu.lv/>" [2023-03-13]

- Consultations on the creation of a sustainable DAS digital infrastructure.
- Transfer of experience on DAS cooperation with data depositors (researchers).

The mentorship activities during 2021–2022

The Latvian request for support mainly concerned installation and use of Dataverse, but at the same time there were no resources for a Dataverse installation. At the start of the Mentorship Programme there was an initiative to transfer some of the resources into a Dataverse training, tailor-made for the mentees. This would have benefited the Latvian mentee, but unfortunately it was not possible to implement this training.

To be able to support the mentee, the mentor reviewed the current situation for the mentee. After the information collection, the mentor suggested the following activities to support the development of the LSSDA:

- Discuss how the operations of a smaller data archive can be built, what kind of competence is needed, necessary human and other resources, documentation services, and how to build a sustainable network. Go through workflows and help create an organisational structure, etc.
- Collect or/and help develop the most necessary documents and prepare them for translation into the national language. Documents in the national language are of great help in reaching out to various stakeholders. Among the most important documents are the mission statement and the development plan.
- Gather information about and, if necessary, help develop the FAIR principles in the various institutions.
- Support Dataverse development, build connections with experts, developers. Discuss needs, problems, possible solutions, etc.
- Update LSSDA's information sheet and other documents.

During the mentoring talks, it was concluded that funding and support at the national level is the most important prerequisite for future development. Once this level is reached, planning to reach the next level can continue. The implementation of the plan above was therefore postponed. LSSDA and TARKI continued to stay in touch during the Mentorship Programme and TARKI was ready to help if circumstances changed in a positive direction. The mentor kept the mentee continuously informed about possible collaborations with other SPs and training programs, such as Dataverse related training events.

The situation at LSSDA at the end of 2022 and plans for 2023

In early 2022, a consortium - the NGO/society 'Higher Education and Science Information Technology Shared Service Centre'²⁰ - was established at the initiative of the Ministry of

²⁰ "Higher Education and Science Information Technology Shared Service Centre: <https://www.vpc.lv/>" [2023-03-06]

Education and Science of the Republic of Latvia. The founders of VPC are the four major universities of Latvia: University of Latvia, Riga Technical University, Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies, and Riga Stradiņš University. Other higher education and science institutions can join as members.

LSA's plan was to create a prototype for a national archive of research data from the humanities and social sciences connected to the DataverseLV. Although not much has happened so far, there are several ways to proceed:

- Approach the Ministry of Education and the VPC Consortium for funding to build a test Dataverse, for example by archiving old and/or orphan datasets.
- Collaborate with organisations involved or interested in the DataverseLV project, especially from the SSH sector in Latvia.
- Collaborate with other CESSDA partners from the region. LiDA, the Lithuanian DAS, has recently updated its IT infrastructure to be based on Dataverse.
- Increase the involvement in the growing Dataverse community within CESSDA.

LSA could also offer the Ministry of Education and the VPC Consortium to be consultants or participants in the planned Data Stewards programme. Thanks to the knowledge gained through participation in the CESSDA network, representatives from LSA have held lectures on the subject of "Research data. Data repositories. Data preparation for publication". The lectures are part of the training program for professional development "Open Science and Science Communication" created by the National Library of Latvia with the participation of staff from libraries and scientific institutions.

Reflections on the mentorship from LSSDA and TARKI

Reflection from LSSDA: At this stage, it is important to improve the data sharing culture in Latvia. Currently, very few people in Latvia understand the potential in this area, which is why there are no private or institutional initiatives to create a DAS. Potentially, it could become a paid service for archiving and publishing research data. This is because the service is increasingly in demand by researchers in Latvia, but they (at least in the social sciences and humanities) do not yet have these skills. It is necessary to start by creating a relevant infrastructure that meets at least a minimum level of data archiving services. Seed money or an active person who can devote time to attracting funds is also needed.

Reflection from TARKI: The Mentorship Programme could contribute to raising awareness of the benefits of the data sharing culture by helping to organise training events or meetings that demonstrate how the research community can benefit from an active DAS. At the same time, the Mentorship Programme together with CESSDA MO should lobby to help the DAS initiative reach the next level. At an early stage of development, gaining official support from the stakeholders is crucial and CESSDA can help with this. At the current level of development, support from an international organisation like CESSDA ERIC is essential to

build a network of stakeholders in Latvia. LSSDA has been a partner organisation of CESSDA for many years and TARKI is of course ready to support its ambitions in the future.

Additional mentorship - CSDA and the Kyiv Archive

The CSDA-Kyiv Archive mentorship was not among the original participants in the Mentorship Programme 2021-2022 but started at CSDA's initiative to support the Kyiv Archive during the war in Ukraine, caused by the full-scale invasion of Russia in February 2022. This mentorship is an in-kind support to the CESSDA Mentorship Programme from CSDA.

The Ukraine National Data Bank of Sociological Data, the "Kyiv Archive", is a Ukrainian data service initiated in 2015 by the Kyiv International Institute of Sociology (KIIS) and the Social Indicators Center, together with the National University of Kyiv-Mohyla Academy. The operation is financed by the International Renaissance Foundation, an integral part of the Open Society Foundations (OSF).

The purpose of the Kyiv Archive is to make data from sociological surveys conducted in Ukraine easily and freely available to any interested person or organisation in Ukraine and outside the country. To date, the Kyiv Archive has mainly been supported by funds from private research institutions and international organisations and is not an official member of CESSDA ERIC. In recent years, the archive has been in contact with CESSDA about the procedures for a membership and more commitment from the archive to adapt to the European standards for handling social data.

Under CSDA's mentorship, the Kyiv Archives successfully received a grant from the International Renaissance Foundation (OSF) in Ukraine to improve the website and support ongoing operations in 2022.

In 2022, four working meetings were held via Zoom on the development of the agreements on data supply and conditions for data cooperation. Other things discussed during the meetings were updates of documents and how they can be standardised to meet international requirements, development of a routine for data storage, and cooperation with data providers and users.

A routine of standardised data collection has been developed for the surveys on Ukrainian-Russian relations, health and well-being of Ukrainians 1993-2022, which will be published by CSDA together with other datasets.

Joint activities are now being planned to be carried out in 2023. These will depend on what financial support and resources the Kyiv Archives will have during the year.

Currently, the mentoring activities are conducted within CSDA's operational activities, and the hope is to engage several CESSDA SPs to support our Ukrainian partner.

Conclusions

In the three Mentorship Programmes to date, 22 countries have been invited to participate. Two thirds of these have participated at least once and more than a quarter of them twice. In the Mentorship Programme 2021-2022, three of the mentee organisations came from a CESSDA ERIC member country and three from a partner country.

The Mentorship Programme 2021-2022 has mainly been conducted through online meetings and with an onsite meeting as the major event. Both mentors and mentees feel that they had a good relationship and that they learn from each other.

For some of the mentorships the onsite visits have been a result of several initiatives, such as between the CESSDA Mentorship Programme and the RIttrainPLUS project in the case of DASS-BiH, and ERASMUS funding in the case of DATICE. Several of the mentees have also simultaneously been supported by projects like SSHOC, EOSC-Nordic and FAIRsFAIR in the work to achieve a CoreTrustSeal certification.

The demand for support in matters concerning Dataverse was greater than the number of mentors with this knowledge. In this case it would have been preferable to be able to provide a tailor-made training event for the mentees.

As has been discussed in earlier reports, the Mentorship Programme in its present shape works best for a DAS that has been institutionalised and where the organisation has a reasonably stable staffing situation. Although the Mentorship Programme often works very well, it may be time to consider its future. A new concept for the Mentorship Programme is presented in another deliverable from the Mentorship Programme 2021-2022.²¹

²¹ Alfredsson, Iris, Bishop, Libby, & Bornatici, Christina. (2023). D2 Strategy for the Development of the Mentorship Programme. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5554455>